

EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION TOWARDS JM FRICTECH INDIA PVT LTD, CHENNAI, TAMILNADU, INDIA: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

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Abstract:

The paper has been done in JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd, Chennai, Tamilnadu. The main objective of the study is concerned with studying the impact of employee job satisfaction at the organizational performance, and to know whether they are satisfied with the services or not. The data has been collected from the employees at JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd, Chennai region. Those collected data were analyzed with the statistical tool of descriptive analysis and percentage analysis and interpreted. This study has individually observed the employees at JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd and study of employee job satisfaction has been provided with suggestions with the consideration of findings.

About JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd:

JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd (JMI), Established in 2008 as a joint Venture between M/s Jimmying Frictech Co Ltd - Korea and NTC Engineering Services Pvt Ltd – India. Design, Develop, Test and Manufacture of Wet Brake & Wet Clutch System with its actuation parts (both Mechanical & Hydraulic Brake Parts). JMI is the most preferred supplier to all Tractor OEMs in India, and we also supply to Construction & Material handling equipment's segments. JMI exports to various OEMs in South America, China and other parts of the world. JMI believes in self-contained facilities with High Precision CNC Controlled Machines and SPMs to ensure the products as per specification.

- Capabilities of Design, Develop, Test & Manufacture the Wet Brake & Clutch System from "One Roof".
- Friction Material (paper, carbon, Kevlar etc.) chosen from its widest range suitable to the application.
- Products are manufactured with "on line" Checking / testing features keeping the criticality of the final product.
- Brake and Clutch are critical for functioning of the end product/ equipment, JMI ensures defect free part with inbuilt "Poke Yoke" System in assembly. Integrated global experience in these part.
- Accredited with ISO 9001:2008 / ISO, 14001:2004 / BS-OHSAS, 18001:2007 Certified Organization.

Significance of the Study:

Employees' satisfaction is the individual employee general attitude towards the job. It is also an employee cognitive and affective evaluation of his or her job. According to New Cranny, Smith and Stone (1992), Employee job satisfaction is defined as the combination of affective reactions to the differential perceptions of what he/she wants to receive compared with what he/she actually receives.

Measuring Job Satisfaction:

There are many methods for measuring job satisfaction. By far, the most common method for collecting data regarding employee job satisfaction is the Likert scale (named after Rensis Likert). Other less common methods of for gauging job satisfaction include: Yes/No questions, True/False questions, point systems, checklist, forced choice answers. The Job Descriptive Index (JDI), created by Smith, Kendall, & Hulin (1969), job satisfaction that has been widely used. It measures one's satisfaction in five facets: pay, promotions and opportunities, coworkers, supervision, and the work itself. The scale is simple, participants answer either yes, no, or decide in response to whether given statements accurately describe one job. The Job in General Index is an overall measurement of job satisfaction. It was an improvement to the job Descriptive Index because the JDI focused too much on individual facets and not enough on work satisfaction in general.

Relative Factors Involved in Job Satisfaction:

- Nature of work
- Working Environment
- Working hours
- Job security
- Responsibility given for the job
- Relationship with colleagues
- Relationship with supervisors
- Safety measures
- Grievance handling
- Wage rate system

- Incentives
- Canteen facilities
- Bonus schemes
- Family welfare measures
- Medical / First Aid facilities
- Recognition
- Rewards

Review of Literature:

Yasemin Oramanet.al (2014) The main objective of the research is to examine employee job satisfaction in a strategic human resource management research with a model of job satisfaction in the Research and Development (R&D) industry should consist of work related factors such getting pay for overtime, giving employees more authority, the possibility of getting promotion in the workplace, employees' participation in decision-making processes and sensitivity of management towards problems at work.

Subhasish Chatterjee, Smriti Priya (2016) Studied on employee job satisfaction in Multi-specialty Hospital in Mumbai the sample size was 105. The data was collected through simple random sampling methods. The statistical tool were used, percentage analysis and U-test. The results shows that most of the employees are satisfied with the management and with their supervisor

Khalil-Ur Rahman, et.al (2017) Examined the job satisfaction of sales agents from Islamic and conventional insurance of Pakistan. The sample size was 318. Data was collected through multi-stage stratified random sampling. The statistical tool were used multiple regression and hierarchal regression model including 11 hygiene- motivational. The result revealed that was. Job satisfaction is any blend of mental physiological and natural circumstances that bring about a man honestly to say I am satisfied by my job.

Khurram Shahzad. Et.al (2017) calculated the mediating impact of job satisfaction on the relationship in Pakistan. The sample size was 190. Data was collected through simple random sampling method. The statistical tool used for research was Correlation Analysis. Descriptive Statistics regression. The Results showed that job satisfaction can be achieved through effective implementation of compensation plans and managing workload.

Somayah Salahshouri Ardestani (2017) Studied on employee job satisfaction and during this process to understand the psychology-employee behavior in Hyderabad-India The sample size was 200. Data was collected through simple random sampling method. The statistical tool was used chi-square test. The results show that if the performance (hospitals Services) falls short of expectations, the employee is dissatisfied and if it matches the expectations, the employee is satisfied.

Ganesh Acharya and Abbokar Siddiq (2018) studied the satisfaction level among the employees looking at working conditions. Grievance handling systems, Relationship with Colleagues, Reward systems, Promotion and Career Development opportunities Job Security Provisions, Personal factors & other factors at Adam sugar mills. The sample size was 120. Data was collected through simple sampling random method. The statistical tool used was chi-square test. The result revealed that good work environment. good reward and good work conditions can increase employee job satisfaction.

Mohammad Hosein Lotfi et.al (2020) This study is analyzing the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction among the employees of Tehran Payame Noor University. Statistical Society of this study includes all personnel of the organization (800 people) in 2012 and the sample size includes 260 people that were selected randomly. This study was of correlational descriptive-analytic type and for data collection, organizational justice (Moorman and Niehoff, 1993) and job satisfaction questionnaires were used. For analyzing the data, statistical methods like Multiple Regression and Pearson Correlation Coefficient were utilized and the results were as follows: There is a significant relationship between organization justice and job satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem:

It is said that satisfied workers is a productive workers any kind of grievance relating to organizational or personal to a greater extent influence on the job. So every organization is giving higher priority to keep their workers with satisfaction by providing several facilities which improves satisfaction & which reduces dissatisfaction. Employee job satisfaction is considered as a key issue by the entrepreneur where efforts are taken & program are initiated. If an workers is not satisfied with the job there are chances for absenteeism, turnover, lower productivity, committing of mistakes, diverting energy for different types of conflicts keeping this thing in view all organization are typing to identify the areas where satisfaction to be improved to get out of the above dangers. In this connection a survey was conducted on behalf of Break industry ltd to identify the level of satisfaction in terms of strongly agree to strongly disagree on various job-related factors.

Objectives of the Study:

The objective of the study is as follows

- To identify the factors which influence the Employee job satisfaction of employees in a breaks manufacturing industry.
- To analyses the employees satisfaction with reference to working hours and leave facilities.
- To study the relationship between employees and their superiors.

- To suggest suitable remedial measures to improve the Employee job satisfaction.
- To study the working environment and working hours.
- To study the safety & welfare measures provide by industry

Hypotheses of the Study:

It means tentative generalization of the validity of which remains the tested. In short it deals with certain assumptions made in the study.

- Null Hypothesis: A hypothesis which assumes that there is no significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called null hypothesis. It is denoted by Ho
- Alternative Hypothesis: A hypothesis which assumes that there is a significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called alternative hypothesis. It is denoted by H1

Research Design and Methodology:

A research design is the specialization of measure and procedure for the information needed to solve problems in the overall operational pattern of framework of the project that stipulates what information is to be collected from which sources by what procedure. There are three types of research design.

- Exploratory Research Design
- Descriptive Research Design
- Experiment Research Design

The research used in the project is Empirical method of research. The study used both primary as well as secondary data. The primary data was collected from the labor of company. The study was conducted with the help of field survey technique among 120 labors in JM Frictech India Pvt Ltd.

Data Sources:

- Primary Data: Primary data are those, which are collected for the first time. They are original in character. The data collected by the investigator for the first time for their own use is usually classed as primary data.
- Secondary Data: Secondary data are those that have already been collected by others. These are usually available in journals, periodicals, dailies, research publication official records etc., they may either be available in published form or in an unpublished form. When it is not possible to collect the data by primary method, the investigator may make use of this method

Statistical Tools Applied:

Statistical tools like simple percentage and chi square used in the compilation and computation of data.

(i) Percentage Analysis, (ii) Chi-Square Test, (iii) Correlation Analysis

The primary data had was collected from the samples from various areas and have been properly arranged, edited and tabulated in a systematic format and analyzed by using appropriate statistical tools. A bipartite correlation and liner regression analysis were carryout using SPSS

Limitation of the Study:

Though the researcher took utmost care and efforts to avoid shortcomings in the process of data collection and analysis, the study is prone to some limitations, which are mentioned below:

- The time taken for my project study was 4 months to gather opinions from the employees.
- The data collected by me through primary source is constrained by the sample size of which is 120 employees.
- The data collected other than questionnaire is from the secondary source only.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: No of Years in Working Service

S.No	No of Years in Working Service	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Below 4 Years	48	40.00%
2	4-8 Years	32	26.70%
3	8-12 Years	29	24.20%
4	Above 12 Years	11	9.20%
	Total	120	100

Source: Data collected from primary

The above table shows that no of years in working service, 40% of the respondents service are below 4 years, 26.7% of the respondents service are 4-8 years, 24.2% of the respondents service are 8-12 years and remaining 9.2% of the respondents service are above 12 years. Majority 40% of the respondents service are below 4 years.

Table 2: Relationship between You and Co-Workers

S.No	Relationship Between You and Co-Worker	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
1	Highly Satisfied	40	33.30%
2	Satisfied	39	32.50%
3	Neutral	20	16.70%

4	Dissatisfied	9	7.50%
5	Highly Dissatisfied	12	10.00%
	Total	120	100

Source: Data collected from primary

The above table inferred that relationship between you and coworkers, 33.3% of the respondents are highly satisfied relationship between coworkers, 32.5% of the respondents are satisfied relationship between coworkers, 16.7% of the respondents are neutral relationship between coworkers, 7.5% of the respondents are dissatisfied relationship between coworkers and remaining 10% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied relationship between coworkers. Majority 32.5% of the respondents are satisfied relationship between coworkers.

Table 3: Satisfied in Safety Measures in the Organization

S.No	Satisfied in Safety Measures in the Organization	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Highly Satisfied	29	24.20%
2	Satisfied	38	31.70%
3	Neutral	38	31.70%
4	Dissatisfied	8	6.70%
5	Highly Dissatisfied	7	5.80%
	Total	120	100

Source: Data collected from primary

The above table shows that satisfied in safety measures in the organization, 24.2% of the respondents are highly satisfied in safety measures in the organization, 31.7% of the respondents are satisfied and neutral in safety measures in the organization, 6.7% of the respondents are dissatisfied in safety measures in the organization and remaining 5.8% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied in safety measures in the organization. Majority 31.7% of the respondents are satisfied and neutral in safety measures in the organization

Conclusion:

The study did not observe any differences between marketers and those working in an office for training satisfaction. The survey found an increase in overall training satisfaction and employee job satisfaction with increase in respondents age; Analyzing job rank, overall satisfaction with training is seen to be increasing with respondents job rank, a similar behavior can be witnessed for Job satisfaction that also show a surge with rise in rank. Besides Training Content satisfaction, the study found Training session Satisfaction, Trainer Satisfaction and Transfer of learning to be significantly positively associated with job satisfaction. This project title “A study on Employees satisfaction” of employees at JM Fricotech India Pvt Ltd Chennai was done among 120 employees in a simple random sample method. From the study it was formed that the employees are Satisfied working in almost in all aspects. Some improvements are suggested by the employees for satisfaction organization can concentrate on that and make the employees fully satisfied. This will help to increase the morale of the employees.

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